

Andrade, Sebastião Marques Carmo de (1939–2019)

THE BRAZILIAN WHITE CENTER – UNASP

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Sebastião Marques Carmo de Andrade
Photo courtesy of Brazilian White Center - UNASP.

Sebastião Marques Carmo de Andrade was an evangelist canvasser in Brazil.

Sebastião Marques Carmo de Andrade was born on August 20, 1939, in Carmo do Cajuru, state of Minas Gerais, Brazil. Son of Joaquim Marques and Maria Custódia de Jesus, he grew up in a poor family and worked since childhood to help in the family subsistence. He had 17 siblings, among them Belisário Marques, a respected Adventist psychologist in Brazil.

Encouraged by Belisário, he moved to São Paulo city at the age of 16 in order to begin secondary education at Brazil College (now UNASP-SP), where he was baptized into the Adventist faith. Afterwards, he completed secondary education at São Paulo Academy (now UNASP-HT), in the city of Hortolândia. There he met Thereza de Carvalho, an accounting student, and they got married in March of 1963. Together they had three children: Daiene Carvalho Marques (Arco) (1965-), Harrison Carvalho Marques (1968-) and Adriene de Carvalho Marques (Köhler) (1970-)?

Following their marriage, they lived for three years in the United States and, on returning to Brazil, Sebastião entered the canvassing work in 1967. In a short time, he reached first place in canvassing sales throughout South America, a position he occupied many times. In 1972, he graduated in Law from Gama Filho University, and in the same year he completed studies in Portuguese and English languages at the Souza Marques Technical Education Foundation, both in Rio de Janeiro city. Although receiving many great job opportunities in other areas, he chose to continue canvassing and worked as a literature evangelist for a total of 40 years. Over his canvassing ministry, he became specialized in selling literature in companies. Among others, he successfully gained access to two big Brazilian Industries – Randon, in the branch of land transportation of cargo, and Votorantin, a multinational with a broad scope of production.³

Sebastião spent his last days in Rio de Janeiro city, where he was an active member of the Madureira and Central churches, participating in the foundation of the church of Vila Valqueire. His last years of life were experienced with Alzheimer's disease, and he died at the age of 80, on May 17, 2019, in the city of Brasília, Federal District. The funeral ceremony was held on May 18 at the Jardim Metropolitano Cemetery in Brasília. Sebastião Andrade is remembered as a passionate literature evangelist, who dedicated his life for preaching the Adventist message through canvassing. Despite the material resources he acquired by this means, the most valuable richness of his ministry were the souls who were reached for Christ through his ministry.⁴

NOTES

1. José Carlos de Lima, "O Defensor da Colportagem," *Revista Adventista*, year 114, n. 1346, June, 2019, 44; Dr. Belisário Marques, to Sergio Micael, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, March 3, 2020; Siqueira, José Luiz, "De Mãos Dadas Com os Filhos," *Revista Adventista*, year 80, n. 08, August, 1985, 5.?
2. Ibid.?
3. Lima, 44; Dr. Belisário Marques, to Sergio Micael, Engenheiro Coelho, São Paulo, March 03, 2020.; Siqueira, 5; Barcelos, Célio, "Sebastião Marques – colportor especializado," *Airós Tempo de Oportunidades*, May 17, 2019. Accessed on March 4, 2020, <http://www.tempodeoportunidade.com.br/2019/05/sebastiao-marques-colportor.html?>
4. Lima, 44.?

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